

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE PLACE OF TEACHING TASKS IN THE ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT OF STUDENTS' ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

The article substantiates the relevance of the research topic, explains the concept of teaching activities, emphasizes that the structure of teaching activities (or tasks), teaching operations, control, the presence of price components, mastery and teaching activities are essentially different events. It is also noted that the teaching tasks require students to discover and master the general solutions (principles, regularities) of various problems and specific practical issues in their teaching activities, by setting learning tasks, the teacher introduces students to a specific learning situation: in this situation, they get acquainted with the content of general methods of solving tasks, taking into account all specific and specific options, acquire relevant knowledge, skills and habits.

The article states that important functions of meta-understanding should be taken into account when applying tasks to organize and manage students' activities, The training to divide creative thinking into analytical and heuristic types is important not only for facilitating students' understanding of mental operations in problem solving, but also for the teacher's practical activity in order to create pedagogical conditions for various mental operations. Questions, tasks and forms of training (work) can be chosen for teaching tasks, their application should focus on constructivism, corporate principles and students' experience in regulating mental activity (formation of certain ideas about cognitive (cognitive) processes in students).

Keywords: learning psychology, mastery, teaching tasks, teaching operations, thinking, intuition, algorithm.

Relevance of the research topic

The organization and management of student activities are subject to adequate improvement in response to the challenges of the ever-evolving educational space. This process of improvement is one of the eternal problems of didactics. Important functions of meta-comprehension are taken into account when applying learning tasks in order to organize and manage students' activities, which are necessary for successful learning, they must be developed by all means, and the relevance of the issue is fully understood from a scientific and methodological point of view. Systematic work should be done in the school in this direction. For this, there must be an argumentation based on scientific and pedagogical grounds on the specific features of teaching tasks, theoretical and technological aspects of approaches to their inclusion in the real pedagogical process. It is clear from the analysis of scientific sources that there are "gaps" in this direction in pedagogical theory. For this reason, there are mistakes in the pedagogical practice in this direction. Despite the above, we claim the relevance of the topic of the article.

Interpretation of research materials

As it is known, training is one of the main concepts of pedagogy. [1;210]. From the first days of its emergence, pedagogical psychology has widely used this concept and studied the psychological problems of

teaching in different directions. In educational psychology, the concept of "student learning activities" was established. The establishment of a new pedagogical thinking, scientific achievements in the field of activity allowed to approach this concept from a new perspective, and the concept of "teaching activity" emerged in pedagogical psychology.

Teaching activity is multifaceted

Although training is an important characteristic of educational activity, it does not cover all its aspects. There are different interpretations of the training. In fact, "training, in the broadest sense of the word, involves the acquisition of new knowledge, skills and habits." [2;150]. However, mastery and teaching activities are essentially different events. While mastery is an integral part of any field of activity, educational activity is a specific form of social activity of the individual, a type of activity. This is a special form and type of student activity. By applying the "system-structural" dialectical approach to teaching activities or L. Bertalanf's idea [4;5-8], its components can be distinguished. [5; 8]. Such a step has been taken in scientific sources. The concept of D.V. Elkonin, V.V. Davidov and others distinguishes the following components in the structure of educational activity: 1) teaching situation (or assignments); 2) educational operations; 3) control; 4) price. [10;48].

If we say that the teaching activity begins with the

solution of educational tasks, we will probably not make a mistake. Although the essence of the “teaching task” is reflected in the meaning of the task, its nature is related to the meaning of “teaching”. Teaching tasks require students to discover and master the general solutions (principles, regularities) of various problems and specific practical issues in their teaching activities. [2;150].

By proposing teaching tasks, the teacher introduces students to a specific teaching situation: in this situation, they get acquainted with the content of general methods of solving tasks, taking into account all specific and specific options, acquire relevant knowledge, skills and habits. There are many peculiarities of teaching tasks. In order to solve teaching tasks, students must master the necessary teaching operations. They can be characterized in terms of general and special character. Thought processes – analysis, composition, comparison, generalization, etc. Has a special place in the structure of educational operations. Thought processes are always carried out by applying them to the content of a particular subject. The formation of teaching operations is directly related to the acquisition of mental activity by students.

The intellectual activity of the student is also dominated by various mental operations obtained in the process of direct education. Most problems are solved by algorithms known to the student. Creative activity includes both known methods and techniques of mental activity, as well as the creation of a new system of activity or the discovery of previously unknown patterns. Therefore, in the process of creative activity, the student discovers a new truth, using both logical reasoning and intuition. Intuition is one of the two forms of mental activity, one of the ways in which a particular form of learning task, especially a problem, can be solved. However, intuitive thinking does not fit into strict rules, it goes beyond the existence of certain stages. There is a kind of “leap” in this process. This is typical of heuristic activity. By the way, V.N. Pushkin sees the essence of heuristic activity in the following: a) an activity that is used to solve non-typical task forms; b) there are receptions that are formed during the solution of the task and can be consciously transferred to other examples of tasks. [9; 21-22]

As a result of research, psychologists have identified that when solving a problem (making the learning situation stationary), the student’s creative mental activity related to the introduction of new information into the existing system of knowledge and its processing can be of two types: analytical and heuristic.

The division of creative thinking into analytical and heuristic types is important not only for facilitating students’ understanding of mental operations in problem solving, but also for the teacher’s practical activity in order to create pedagogical conditions for the implementation of individual mental operations. It is known that training is important for the coordination of both types of mental activity in solving the problem. Of course, training can have some kind of advantage, depending on the nature of the problem and other facts, which is natural. The analytical type of mental activity

is related to the exact sequence of mental actions during the solution of the problem, the existing solution algorithm. Analysis and synthesis, generalization, abstraction and concretization – these mental operations follow each other, in a certain sequence, in stages, step by step, step by step, to solve the problem. The direction of thinking is determined by the relationship between the given and the sought, the solution is found by trial and error. When the appropriate rules are chosen correctly, the algorithmic logic of thinking often leads to a solution.

In modern psychology, C. Bruner tried to reveal the difference between intuitive thinking and analytical thinking. He compared analytical and intuitive thinking: “... analytical thinking is characterized by the fact that its various stages are clearly imagined, it is possible to express the whole with speech. In this case, the student is able to understand the course and content of thought, and the mind is able to accept judgment in the form of a transition from general to specific, especially general. Intuitive thinking is the basis of the heuristic type of mental activity. [7;53-54]

It is important for a teacher to know the characteristics of this or that type of mental activity in order to formulate teaching tasks without making mistakes and incorporate them into the real pedagogical process, to manage the teaching-cognitive process at the desired level. The structure of the analytical type of mental activity has become known in pedagogy and psychology. These are: 1) perception of the difficulty and analysis of the problem situation; 2) identification of the main difficulty; 3) application of known algorithms or search for analytical solutions; 4) check the solution and its correctness. [8;119]. The structure of the heuristic type of mental activity can be fundamentally different. Its individual stages are close to the stages of the analytical type, but their specificity is not absent. [3;69-72]. The structure of the heuristic activity is as follows: 1) perception of difficulty and analysis of the problem situation; 2) identification of the main difficulty and formula of the problem; 3) a) search for solutions and their development (development of a new algorithm) by making hypotheses, or b) hypothesis and intuitive solution; 4) check the validity of the hypothesis by applying the obtained result in practice. Undoubtedly, the second way improves the practice of managing the process of developing students’ mental abilities. [3;119]

It is no coincidence that Flevell emphasizes the importance of control over the organization of attention and problem-solving in the analysis of meta-cognitive functions. Supervision is directly related to assessment, which is an important part of teaching activities.

When the learning activity is formed, the student becomes the subject of his activity, qualitatively new features appear in his learning motivation. Psychologically favorable conditions are created for the actualization of cognitive interests in educational activities.

Self-awareness has always been a topical issue in world philosophy, psychology and pedagogy. They approached the self-perception of a person from the point of view of personality, and did not appreciate the

fact that a person understands the features of his mental world, the world of thinking, and cognitive processes. Therefore, important functions of meta-understanding should be taken into account when applying tasks to organize and manage student activities. Among these functions, the American psychologist Flayvell includes the following: 1) Problem statement and identification of possible solutions; 2) Know what cognitive process is necessary to solve the task; 3) Activation of cognitive rules and methods; 4) Belief in the possibilities of thinking; 5) Attempt to solve tasks more efficiently. According to P. Massen, J. Kencer, J. Cogan and A. Houston, these functions develop to some extent in all children. However, their upbringing has a significant impact on their level of development. These features are a prerequisite for successful training. They need to be developed by all means. The urgency of the issue must be understood in all scientific and methodological ways, and systematic work must be done at school in this area. [2 ;64-65]

Commenting on these functions, Prof. A.A. Alizadeh emphasizes that "... these functions are interrelated. The first function is due to the formation of students' ideas about the goals of the activity. As they continue their activities, they learn to apply known ways to different situations. Gradually, students develop ideas about cognitive processes. They understand that in order to memorize the material, the teacher needs to listen carefully and remember it. When the student has a clear idea of these psychological processes, he forms attention in one case and memory in another, depending on the nature of the task. In this process, his skills gradually increase: he is looking for new ways to solve the problem. When a student believes in the possibilities of his thinking, he does not shy away from difficulties, even if he fails, he thinks and tries to solve the problem. In this process, his attitude to himself changes. He solves the task in an efficient way, not in a hurry. [2; 64]

In contrast to the above, it is concluded that questions, tasks and forms of training can be chosen for teaching tasks, their application focuses on constructivism, corporate principles and the experience of regulating students' mental activity (formation of certain ideas about cognitive processes in students). Should be drawn to the center.

In the system in which it is applied, the teaching tasks should determine the appropriate teaching situation; must be appropriate to the age, knowledge and intellectual level, abilities and interests of students, have a differential character; should be based on the state program and national values; be relevant, relevant to real life and students' experiences; should be interesting, engaging, exploring; must be clearly stated; should include clear and open-ended questions.

The formation of learning tasks is only one part of the work that aims to develop students' learning activities in a system that includes them. One of the important issues is to ensure that students develop cognitive activity while working on tasks and maintain it (continuously) throughout the process. It should be noted that the four main mechanisms of the active (interactive)

system (the key to this process is research) are the formation and maintenance of cognitive activity. These are: the creation of a problem situation (the student is presented with a problem formulated as a teaching task, and as a result of focusing on solving the problem, cognitive activity arises); the student acts as a researcher, the teacher as a facilitator (during the application of the active (interactive) system, the student must stand as a subject, be an equal participant in this process, he must acquire knowledge independently during the research); the need for dialogue and cooperation (active (interactive) process is conducted in a dialogical manner in a collaborative environment); psychological support: respect and trust (the means of maintaining students' cognitive activity is their psychological support, which is possible due to the teacher's kindness, respect and trust in students, confidence in their abilities). [6; s.49-50].

It is possible for a student to act as a researcher if the content of the training material, the form of movement of tools and methods (in the learning process, the content of the training material, tools and methods act in the context of the organization) correspond to the research process. The organizational form of training based on the research process has its own structure, the structure of the active (interactive) lesson is reminiscent of the stages of the research process.

Scientific novelty of the research

The specific features of the teaching tasks, the theoretical and technological aspects of the approaches related to their inclusion in the real pedagogical process were clarified in accordance with the scientific and pedagogical bases.

Theoretical significance of the research

The gaps in the theory related to the theoretical and technological aspects of the inclusion of teaching tasks in the real pedagogical process have been largely eliminated.

Practical significance of the research

The existence of scientific and pedagogical interpretation of the specific features of teaching tasks, the theoretical and technological aspects of the approaches to their inclusion in the real pedagogical process has a positive impact on the formation of an environment adequate to eliminate errors in pedagogical practice.

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